

Compilation of the layers of marine environment and ecosystem (created in WP2), species distribution and habitat (created in WP3), and blue carbon (created in WP4) ready for prioritisation analysis

Deliverable 5.1

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 5.1 overview

The WP5 *Prioritisation* utilises the results of WP2 (*Ecosystem and connectivity modelling*), WP3 (*Species and biogenic habitat distribution*), and WP4 (*Blue carbon*) to implement additional biodiversity assessments and to conduct a prioritization analysis for designing MPA network for biodiversity conservation and blue carbon. Through the prioritization, 10% and 30% of European seas will be identified as optimal MPA networks for biodiversity, blue carbon and both together. This deliverable reports the detailed information of each environmental, ecosystem classification, species and habitat, and organic carbon in sediments (representing stores of blue carbon) layer produced under the MPA Europe project and which will be used directly in the prioritisation analysis.

Introduction

Systematic Conservation Planning (SCP) is a technique that emerged in the 1980s (Kirkpatrick, 1983) to guide objective data-driven decisions about where the location of protected areas would optimise the inclusion of species and/or other measures of biodiversity (Boulton et al., 2023; Kirkpatrick, 1983). These SCP approaches use complementarity-based optimization algorithms (Kirkpatrick, 1983) and require a conservation attributes standardised over the entire study area, so it must use species ranges rather than point data subject to sampling bias. The objective of the Deliverable 5.1 is to compile all the spatial layers created under MPA Europe and check that the data for the prioritisation are ready for use. The WP5 *Prioritisation* will leverage the outcomes of WP2 (*Ecosystem and connectivity modelling*), WP3 (*Species and biogenic habitat distribution*), and WP4 (*Blue carbon*) to perform further biodiversity assessment and a prioritization analysis for designing an MPA network aimed at biodiversity conservation and blue carbon. The process will identify optimal MPA networks covering 10% and 30% of European seas, targeting biodiversity, organic carbon and the integration of both objectives.

The biological data include species distribution ranges, species that form (biogenic) habitats such as seagrass and kelp, and new maps of ecosystems as a measure of functional biodiversity. In addition to the proposed work, we have re-analysed species distributions to objectively define biogeographic regions in all European seas. Future analysis will examine how these align with environmentally defined ecosystems. Mean annual environmental data layers, including organic carbon, will not be directly used in the prioritisation analysis but used to visualise the environmental context of the biodiversity variables and prioritisation results.

Materials

Environmental variables

Spatially complete and standardized environmental data layers for the European seas were developed using the state-of-the-art computational pipelines of Bio-ORACLE v2.0 (Assis et al, 2018), and a wave exposure index based on wave fetch (Burrow et al. 2023 and references therein). Under the MPA Europe WP2 we produced a collection of ecologically relevant environmental data layers specifically designed for bioclimatic modelling. These represent climatological conditions, showing the annual averages of each variable by decade from 2000 to 2020 (for present-day conditions) and from 2030 to 2100 (for future climate changes) (Assis et al., 2023). The following environmental layers have been prepared and used to support the analyses performed under the WP2-4 (for further details, see Table 1):

- *Air temperature* (°C): the temperature of the air at a height of 1.5 to 2 m above the ocean.
- *Bathymetry* (m): the depth of water.
- *Current speed* (m s^{-1}): the speed of sea water movement.
- *Diffuse attenuation coefficient (Kd)* (m^{-1}): the light dissipation as it penetrates deeper into seawater.
- *Distance to coast* (km): distance of any point in the sea to the nearest coastline at intervals of 0.05 degrees.
- *Mixed layer depth* (m): the depth to which the seawater is well mixed, typically until it reaches a pycnocline or thermocline.
- *Nitrate concentration* (mmole m^{-3}): the amount of dissolved nitrate in the seawater.
- *Oxygen concentration* (mmole m^{-3}): the amount of dissolved molecular oxygen in the seawater.
- *pH* (unitless): the concentration of hydrogen ions (H^+) in the seawater.

- *Phosphate concentration* (mmole m⁻³): the amount of dissolved phosphate in the seawater.
- *Photosynthetically available radiation (PAR)*: the measurement of the daily solar radiation within the 400 to 700 nm wavelength range, utilized by photosynthetic organisms during the process of photosynthesis. Unit: millimoles of light energy per square meter per day.
- *Phytoplankton concentration* (mmol m⁻³): the phytoplankton abundance in the seawater.
- *Salinity*: the amount of dissolved salt in the seawater.
- *Seabed slope* (unitless): the depth changes over distance indicating the inclination or gradient of the seabed.
- *Sea bottom temperature* (°C): the temperature of the water next to the seafloor.
- *Sea ice cover* (percentage): the depth of sea ice on the seawater.
- *Sea surface temperature (SST)* (°C): the temperature of the seawater at to the surface, usually with the first 5 mm depth.
- *Terrain ruggedness, topographic heterogeneity, or rugosity* (unitless): the difference in depth between adjacent cells of the seabed. It indicates benthic habitat complexity.
- *Wave fetch* (unitless): measurement of the wave exposure based on the distance over water that the wind blows in a single direction or the area in which ocean waves are generated by the wind. Wave exposure is the summed of wave fetch (distance to the nearest land in angular sectors around locations of interests), fetch orientation (the weighted mean angle of fetch vectors) and fetch directionality (the weighted standard deviation of fetch orientation).

These data are provided at 0.05 degrees (~5 km) spatial resolution for both present-day and future conditions as generation of climate change shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs) scenarios (Deliverable 2.1, Assis et al. 2023 for further details).

Ecosystem and Biogeographic classification

A first classifications of marine ecosystems in Europe, spanning from the surface to the seafloor, have been developed under the MPA Europe WP2 (*Ecosystem and connectivity modelling*) ([Deliverable 2.3](#) and [Deliverable 2.4](#), Campoy et al., 2023ab). A step forward has been done modelling a depth-integrated marine ecosystem classification for Europe (0-2,500 m depth and seabed) using a wide range of spatially complete and standardised environmental data that reflect both ecosystem conditions and functioning ([Deliverable 2.5](#) and [Deliverable 2.6](#), Campoy et al., 2024ab). In the scope and for the purposes of the MPA Europe project, ‘**ecosystems**’ are defined as “*enduring, spatially bounded environments where biological and energy interactions are greater within than with other ecosystems*” (Zhao et al. 2019).

The final three-dimensional approach for the depth-integrated ecosystem classification included nine ecologically meaningful environmental variables for the waters of European seas (i.e., mixed layer depth, ocean temperature, pH, salinity, sea ice cover, and oxygen, nitrate, phosphate and phytoplankton concentrations) and 15 data layers were included for each environmental variable corresponding to depths from 0 to 2,500 m (i.e., 0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200, 250, 500, 750, 1,000, 1,500, 2,000, and 2,500 m depth) and the near seabed). The hierarchical k-means clustering resulted in four (k = 4), seven (k = 7) and 13 (k = 13) well-defined clusters of ecosystems, and the former were chosen as the primary solution for European waters, each associated with distinct environmental characteristics, each associated with distinct environmental characteristics ([Deliverable 2.6](#), Campoy et al., 2024b).

In addition to what was proposed, we have analysed the distribution of species in European seas to update earlier global analyses of marine biogeography based on endemism. The results indicate several regions of endemism which will be compared with the collection of ecosystems defined at

different depths to objectively define a biologically and ecologically set of biogeographic regions to use in the prioritisation analysis.

Species and biogenic habitat distribution

The biological diversity component of the MPA Europe was developed under the WP3 (*Species and biogenic habitat distribution*) where the additional occurrence and records information for marine species were compiled reaching a total of ~35,000 species registered in OBIS (Figure 1, [Deliverable 3.1](#), Principe et al., 2023a). In addition, datasets of marine species and habitats of conservation importance in Europe were assembled, retrieving information from European policies and other main sources ([Deliverable 3.4](#), Principe et al., 2024).

The environmental niches and geographic distribution of at least 10,000 marine species were modelled across European Seas using 12 environmental variables (i.e., air temperature, bathymetry, distance to coast, nitrate and oxygen concentrations, photosynthetically available radiation, salinity, sea ice cover, sea surface temperature, sea water velocity, rugosity and wave fetch). Additionally, habitat distribution maps were produced by aggregating species distribution models of habitat-forming species and representing different biogenic habitats. The distribution models considering projected scenarios for both the current and future five climate SSP scenarios across two time periods (2050 and 2100) ([Deliverable 3.2](#) and [Deliverable 3.3](#), Principe et al., 2023bc).

Organic carbon in sediments

WP4 mapped organic carbon (OC) levels and storage in marine sediments across European seas as one measure of blue carbon stores. It showed the difference of OC content in vegetated and non-vegetated sediments ([Deliverable 4.1](#) and [Deliverable 4.2](#), Graversen et al., 2023ab) and in relation to EUSeaMap seabed substrata (i.e., coarse sediment, fine mud, mixed sediment, sandy mud or muddy sand, sand, biocenosis of *Posidonia oceanica*, etc.) ([Deliverable 4.3](#), Lønborg et al., 2024). Finally, the spatial extent and standardized OC data in marine sediments of ~5,000 samples across the European seas were converted into a map of carbon storage capacity for European marine habitats ([Deliverable 4.5](#), Addamo et al. 2024) and their associated organic carbon index¹ (Figure 2, [Deliverable 4.4](#), Graversen et al., 2024), which is relevant for the designation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

Conclusions

Spatial data layers of marine ecosystem and biogeographical clusters, species and biogenic habitat range distribution, and terrain ruggedness will be used directly in the prioritisation analysis, while environmental variables and organic carbon layers will be used for further analyses planned under the different tasks of WP5 that will support the prioritisation decisions and the designation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in European seas.

¹ 'Organic carbon index (OCI)' replaces the term 'Blue carbon index (BCI)' used in the former deliverables. This change is made in order to avoid any misleading information. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has defined Blue Carbon (BC) as "all biologically driven carbon fluxes and storage in marine systems that are amenable to management", and although the OC storage capacity of marine sediment is included in the definition, it is only one part of the BC process. Hereafter, OC and OCI are used under the MPA Europe framework.

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Table 1. Environmental variables used under MPA Europe. EC =ecosystem classification; HDMs = habitat distribution models; OC = organic carbon; SDMs = species distribution models.

Environmental variable	Work package (WP)	Main goal	Associated deliverable(s) (D)
Air temperature	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
Bathymetry	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Current speed	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Diffuse attenuation coefficient	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Distance to coast	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Mixed layer depth	WP2	EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
Nitrate concentration	WP2	EC – surface waters	D2.3
		EC – near seabed waters	D2.4
		EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Oxygen concentration	WP2	EC – surface waters	D2.3
		EC – near seabed waters	D2.4
		EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
pH	WP2	EC – surface waters	D2.3
		EC – near seabed waters	D2.4
		EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
Phosphate concentration	WP2	EC – surface waters	D2.3
		EC – near seabed waters	D2.4
		EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Phytoplankton concentration	WP2	EC – surface waters	D2.3
		EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
Photosynthetically available radiation	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Salinity	WP2	EC – surface waters	D2.3
		EC – near seabed waters	D2.4
		EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Seabed slope	WP2	EC – near seabed waters	D2.4
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5
Sea bottom temperature	WP2	EC – near seabed waters	D2.4
		EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
Sea ice cover	WP2	EC – surface waters	D2.3
		EC – depth integrated	D2.5 ; D2.6
	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
Sea surface temperature	WP2	EC – surface waters	D2.3
	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
Terrain ruggedness	WP2	EC – near seabed waters	D2.4
	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
	WP4	OC	D4.5
Wave fetch	WP3	SDMs; HDMs	D3.2 ; D3.3
	WP4	OC	D4.3; D4.5

Figure 1. The marine species distribution data available in OBIS, including ~ 35,000 species (top) and > 67,000,000 individual species distribution records (bottom). Please note that colour scale is adjusted in Log₁₀.

Figure 2. Map of 3-level scale organic carbon index (OCI) for the predicted organic carbon with OC sampling points (OC in percentage) overlaid by the OC data from the field samples in the MPA Europe database. The resolution of predictions is 1 km (Addamo et al. 2024).

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